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Cryptic diversity in a saline Mediterranean pond: the role of salinity and temperature in the emergence of zooplankton egg banks

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Abstract:	<p>Mediterranean endorheic wetlands are strongly affected by local meteorological events, so that they undergo frequent unpredictable disturbances, such as episodes of high salinity or desiccation. In this context, salinity and temperature may be crucial for determining the structure of zooplankton communities and regional biodiversity, since they may trigger the hatching of egg bank in different ways. The goal of this study is to assess the combined role of these two variables on the zooplankton assemblage emerging from the egg bank. We hypothesize that temperature and salinity affect the community structure in a non-linear way, that is, both factors interact and modify the magnitude of their effects. We performed a laboratory factorial design where the same sediment was incubated under different thermal and salinity conditions, reducing the potential effects of other possible confusion factors. Community structure was described by measuring cumulative abundances, species composition, richness and diversity. Our results showed that the community structure was strongly determined by salinity at all experimental temperatures. In contrast, the magnitude of the temperature effect depended on salinity. The high variability among replicates when salinity and temperature increased, suggests that climate change might lead to unpredictable patterns of the community emerging from the egg bank.</p>
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1 **Cryptic diversity in a saline Mediterranean pond: the role of salinity and temperature in**
2 **the emergence of zooplankton egg banks**

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26 **ABSTRACT**

27 Mediterranean endorheic wetlands are strongly affected by local meteorological events, so
28 that they undergo frequent unpredictable disturbances, such as episodes of high salinity or
29 desiccation. In this context, salinity and temperature may be crucial for determining the
30 structure of zooplankton communities and regional biodiversity, since they may trigger the
31 hatching of egg bank in different ways. The goal of this study is to assess the combined role
32 of these two variables on the zooplankton assemblage emerging from the egg bank. We
33 hypothesize that temperature and salinity affect the community structure in a non-linear
34 way, that is, both factors interact and modify the magnitude of their effects. We performed
35 a laboratory factorial design where the same sediment was incubated under different thermal
36 and salinity conditions, reducing the potential effects of other possible confusion factors.
37 Community structure was described by measuring cumulative abundances, species
38 composition, richness and diversity. Our results showed that the community structure was
39 strongly determined by salinity at all experimental temperatures. In contrast, the magnitude
40 of the temperature effect depended on salinity. The high variability among replicates when
41 salinity and temperature increased, suggests that climate change might lead to unpredictable
42 patterns of the community emerging from the egg bank.

43 **Keywords:** egg bank; zooplankton; Mediterranean ponds; salinity; temperature.

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49 INTRODUCTION

50 Wetlands in drylands are strongly affected by local meteorological events, particularly
51 precipitation and temperature patterns. Owing to this strong climatic influence, these
52 ecosystems undergo frequent unpredictable disturbances, such as episodes of high salinity or
53 desiccation. This changing environment translates into a marked year-on year variability on
54 both biotic and abiotic variables, which in turn results in zooplankton assemblages that changes
55 from a physical-controlled pattern (saline stress) to a biological controlled pattern –dominance
56 of grazing, competition– (Castro, 2004). Shortened hydroperiods may emphasise the issue of
57 increased salinity, enhancing internal nutrient recycling and bringing about drastic changes to
58 the composition of zooplankton communities and in the trophic status and food webs of these
59 ecosystems (Beklioglu et al., 2007; Gilbert et al., 2017, 2021; Florencio et al., 2020).

60 The organisms living in these water bodies have developed strategies that allow them to survive
61 and develop in very fluctuating and unpredictable conditions. One such strategy is the formation
62 of resting structures that let the species escape in space (i.e., dispersal by currents, wind,
63 waterfowl) and in time. Many organisms, from microbial eukaryotes (Esteban & Finlay, 2003;
64 Galotti et al., 2014), to rotifers (Declerck & Papakostas, 2017) and crustaceans (Lenormand et
65 al., 2018), can withstand unfavourable environmental conditions in the form of inactive cysts,
66 spores, diapausing eggs or other dormant stages, until there are favourable conditions for
67 growth. Entrance and exit in a dormancy stage can affect the ecosystem structure, both on a
68 population and community level, influencing how these populations will respond to
69 environmental changes. Egg banks extend overlaps in generations, which can play an important
70 role in maintaining diversity in a fluctuating environment when different types (species or
71 genotypes) are favoured at different times (Hairston & Kearns, 2002). Therefore, it is very
72 important to know what environmental factors trigger that each species to leave their dormant
73 stages.

74 In literature, a great deal of research can be found on the role of temperature and photoperiod
75 in the end of dormancy (see Gyllström & Hansson, 2004, and cites inside); somewhat less
76 abundant are the works on the role of salinity (Newton & Mitchell, 1999; García-Roger et al.,
77 2008; Waterkeyn et al., 2010, 2011; Branstrator et al., 2013; Mabidi et al., 2018). Data on the
78 combined effect of temperature and salinity are even scarcer, they have been performed in other
79 types of aquatic ecosystems or do not collect the entire zooplankton community (Newton &
80 Mitchell, 1999; Bailey et al., 2006; Conde-Porcuna et al., 2018).

81 In saline Mediterranean ponds salinity is expected to be crucial determining community
82 structure as it fluctuates greatly, both seasonally and interannually. Although high temperatures
83 can increase salinity due to evaporation, the saline status depends mainly on the general
84 precipitation regime and local hydrogeology. Thus, salinity can be as important as photoperiod
85 and temperature in causing the hatching of resting eggs, as well as in determining the structure
86 of the communities by encouraging one species to hatch instead of another (López-González et
87 al., 1998). This might be particularly important in the current context of global change since an
88 increase in both temperature and salinity is expected; consequently, the potential combined
89 effects of both variables should be considered. On the other hand, a decrease in salinity of
90 endorheic saline ponds is also possible due to the intensive irrigation of agricultural lands with
91 water from other sub-basins.

92 Zooplankton is key to many ecological functions in wetlands; they are important in nutrient
93 cycling (Merritt et al., 1984) and provide trophic support for many species. Knowing the
94 mechanism which determines the behaviour and dynamics of zooplankton egg banks might be
95 crucial for preserving cryptic biodiversity and the resilience of wetlands, which play an
96 important role in the maintenance of regional biodiversity (Gilbert et al., 2014, 2015), and are

97 globally the most common and widespread inland bodies of water (Downing et al., 2006;
98 Downing, 2010).

99 The main goal of our study was to analyse how the combined effect of temperature and salinity
100 influence zooplankton assemblages emerging from egg banks in Mediterranean saline ponds.
101 We expect that species abundances, richness, and diversity increase with the temperature and
102 decrease with salinity. On the other hand, we assume that both variables interact in a non-linear
103 way. We hypothesised that under stress conditions, such as increased salinity and temperature,
104 the species composition emerging from the egg bank might become heterogeneous and
105 unpredictable with different zooplankton assemblages between replicates.

106 To test these, we performed an experimental design where the same sediment was incubated
107 under different thermal and salinity conditions. We measured the abundances, richness, and
108 diversity of the microcrustaceans and rotifers hatching in each treatment group. Unlike in field
109 studies, this controlled scenario reduces the potential effects of possible confusion factors and
110 enables us to gain a clearer insight into the role salinity and temperature play on the hatching
111 pattern, as well as their potential interactive effect.

112

113 **METHODS**

114 *Study site and sampling*

115 Sediment was collected from the Laguna Honda Natural Reserve (Alcaudete, Jaén: 37° 35'
116 54''N; 4° 8' 34''W), a non-coastal permanent athalasoaline shallow inland pond (460 m a.s.l.)
117 located in an endorheic area in the Guadalquivir river watershed (Andalusia, southern Spain)
118 and with a basin surface of 9.94 ha (Castro et al., 2003). As naturally happens in most of the
119 endorheic ponds of this region, there are no fishes in Laguna Honda. Its biological communities

120 have adapted to an environment characterized by a marked year-on-year variability on both
121 biotic and abiotic variables (Guerrero & Castro, 1997; López-González et al., 1998).

122 Laguna Honda is primarily mesosaline, and is occasionally hypersaline or hyposaline. Its water
123 is saline chloride, with a predominance of sodium chloride –Cl-Na-Mg-SO₄ chemical subtype–
124 (Castro, 2004). Maximum depth is 3.16 meters, it is only reached in especially wet periods.

125 In extraordinary periods of drought, Laguna Honda can dry completely: the last times this
126 happened was in the summer of 1995 and, more recently, in late 2021, that is, this pond has
127 been permanent for more than two decades. Laguna Honda experiences large fluctuations in
128 the water level (Fig. 1) and, therefore, in its salinity. The highest salinity recorded by our
129 research team at Laguna Honda has been upper 300 g/L, in 1995 (Guerrero & Castro, 1997); in
130 contrast, the lowest was 8.68 g/L, in July 2014. On the day the samples were taken, the salinity
131 of the pond was 9.12 g/L.

132 Consequently, dormant organisms with very different halotolerance ranges remain in the egg
133 bank of Laguna Honda, waiting for years for favorable conditions that allow them to hatch. All
134 these characteristics make Laguna Honda a perfect natural laboratory for studying the role of
135 temperature and salinity in the structure of the community emerging from the egg bank.

136 In the first fortnight of August 2014, samples of sediment were collected randomly with a KC
137 Kajak Sediment Core sampler (5 cm internal diameter) at five sampling stations placed at an
138 intermediate depth from 2 to 2.5m deep (Fig. 1). The first 5 cm of each corer were collected. In
139 order to have enough sediment, in each sampling station three pseudo-replicates were taken,
140 which were mixed and homogenized manually in the storage bag. Sediment of each sampling
141 station were separately stored. In this way, we have 5 replicates for the following experiments.
142 Samples were transported under cold and dark conditions to the laboratory. Then in the lab,
143 sediment were air dried, separately, for at least 5 months to ensure that only resting structures

144 remained before hatching experiments were set up (Ning et al., 2008, 2010; Ning & Nielsen,
145 2011).

146 *Experimental design*

147 A fully crossed 2 x 3 factorial design was performed, with two levels for *temperature* factor
148 (20°C and 25°C) and three levels for *salinity* factor: S1 (15 g/L; 14.40 mS/cm), S2 (26.72 g/L;
149 24.78 mS/cm) and S3 (45 g/L; 34.61 mS/cm). These ranges of salinity and temperature were
150 chosen because it occurs more frequently in Laguna Honda. Each combination (treatment) was
151 replicated 5 times (each sampling station corresponds to one replicate). Water salinity was
152 estimated by measuring water conductivity and looking for its equivalence in g/L in regression
153 lines of conductivity *versus* salinity (Jiménez-Melero, 2007).

154 Water from Laguna Honda, previously filtered through a Whatman GFC filter, was taken to the
155 experimental salinities by dilution-evaporation processes. When dilution was necessary,
156 distilled water was added. For evaporation, water was softly warmed with a heater.

157 For each treatment, 10 g of dry sediment was placed in a one-liter glass beaker (10 cm Ø). Each
158 beaker was filled with 500 mL of the previously prepared water at the desired salinity. Beakers
159 were partially closed to prevent excessive evaporation and incubated in a cultivation chamber
160 at the temperature of interest. Photoperiod was 12 hours dark and 12 hours light.

161 The water in the beakers was gently filtered (40 µm mesh size) and the captured individuals
162 were examined under a binocular microscope (Leica MZ12.5) twice a week for two months.

163 Water was oxygenated with air bubbles at every check, and renewed fortnightly. In order to
164 prevent reproduction, any newborns detected were immediately removed by means of a Pasteur
165 pipette. They were individually placed on cell-tissue plates, incubated at the same experimental
166 conditions that the origin beaker, and fed on a mixed diet of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* and
167 *Tetraselmis suecica* algae until they reached an age at which they could be identified

168 taxonomically. Since in Iberian saline ponds there usually is only one species of ostracod, and
169 exceptionally a maximum of two coexist (Baltanás et al., 1990), to achieve a trade-off between
170 estimates precision and time management, ostracods were not identified at the species level.
171 We record the abundances of each species (or taxa) accumulated after 60 days of incubation.

172 *Statistical analysis*

173 A shade plot was used to visualize the abundance patterns of taxa on the 6 treatments after 60
174 days of incubation (Clarke & Gorley, 2015). A non-metric multi-dimensional scaling (nMDS)
175 ordination plot based on the Bray-Curtis similarities among treatments was performed; the
176 closer points are to each other the more similar is their community composition (Clarke &
177 Gorley, 2015). Success of the ordination was measured by a stress coefficient (Clarke et al.,
178 2014).

179 To detect differences in community composition between treatments after 60 days at different
180 salinity and temperature conditions, a multivariate analysis of the community data was
181 performed using a Permutational Analysis of Variance (PERMANOVA). This analysis was
182 undertaken with 9999 permutations on Bray-Curtis similarity matrices. A significant result for
183 a given factor from PERMANOVA could signify that the groups differ in their *location*, in their
184 *dispersion* or some combination of the two (Anderson et al., 2008). In order to measure and test
185 homogeneity of multivariate dispersions among treatments, a test of homogeneity of
186 dispersions (PERMDISP) was performed. In addition, the routine MVDISP provided by
187 PRIMER v.7 software gave a description of relative multivariate variability within each of the
188 groups in a single ordination. PERMDISP and MVDISP can help us to test our hypothesis that
189 under stress conditions, such as increased salinity and temperature, the zooplankton
190 assemblages (i.e. abundances and species composition) might become heterogeneous between
191 replicates.

192 Finally, a Similarity Percentage Analyses (SIMPER) was performed to identify both the species
193 characteristic of each treatment (i.e. the contribution that each species makes to the similarity
194 within the group) and the discriminating species between treatments (i.e. which species
195 contribute to the differences between zooplankton assemblages) (Clarke & Gorley, 2015).

196 PRIMER v7 software was used for performed all these analyses. Data were previously fourth-
197 root transformed in order to reduce the influence of more abundant species and increase the
198 influence of rarer species in the analysis (Clarke et al., 2014).

199 Several two-way ANOVAs were performed to detect potential effects of salinity, temperature
200 and their interaction on the abundances of the characteristic species identified previously by
201 SIMPER analysis. When necessary, data were transformed for fulfilling normality and
202 homogeneity of variance assumptions. When no transformation satisfied these assumptions, a
203 Generalized Linear Model (GLM) was performed (Quinn and Keouh, 2002).

204 Similarly, any possible effect of salinity, temperature and their interaction on taxonomic
205 richness and diversity (Shannon-Wiener's diversity index) was separately tested with two-way
206 ANOVA. Richness data were transformed to satisfy the normality assumption (Box-Cox: $\lambda =$
207 0.3775; Log likelihood = -22.595). STATISTICA 13.3 software was used for ANOVA and
208 GLM analyses.

209 **RESULTS**

210 In total 14 taxa were found (Fig. 2). Rotifers were the group with the highest taxonomic
211 richness: *Brachionus* sp., *Lecane luna* (Müller, 1776), *Lecane* sp., *Lepadella patella* (Müller,
212 1773), *Asplanchna* sp., *Ascomorpha* sp., *Hexarthra fennica* (Levander, 1892), unidentified
213 individuals of the superorder Gnesiotrocha and other unidentified rotifers (from now on "taxa
214 Rotifera"). Next in richness were branchiopods with three species: *Pleuroxus letourneuxi*

215 (Richard, 1888), *Daphnia mediterranea* (Alonso, 1985) and *Daphnia magna* (Strauss, 1820).
216 Just one copepod species was found, *Arctodiaptomus salinus* (Daday 1885).

217 ***Role of temperature and salinity on zooplankton assemblage***

218 Figure 2 shows the abundance of the 14 taxa in the different treatments. Note that data are
219 fourth-root transformed, this way 3 and 6 represent 81 and 1296 individuals, respectively. It
220 should be stressed the singularity of the genus *Daphnia* in this research; only six *D.*
221 *mediterranea* individuals were found, all of them at 20°C. *D. magna* was even rarer and only
222 three individuals appeared in one of the replicates at 25°C and S1. In contrast, the other
223 branchiopod, *P. letourneuxi*, was very abundant in some of the treatments. *A. salinus*, ostracods
224 and rotifers occurred in all the treatments.

225 The non-metric multi-dimensional scaling (nMDS) ordination plot based on the Bray-Curtis
226 similarities (Fig. 3) shows a gradient in community structure from S3 to S1 (along MDS axis
227 1), from 20°C to 25°C (along MDS axis 2) and a potential interaction between salinity and
228 temperature (MDS axis 3). The 2-d and 3-d stress level were low, 0.15 and 0.09 respectively.
229 A greater dispersion is observed at S3, at both temperatures; while S1 and S2 at 20°C have less
230 dispersion. Indeed, a test of homogeneity of multivariate dispersions has shown that dispersion
231 is not significant for “salinity” factor (PERMDISP: $F_{2,27} = 3.3701$; $p = 0,0732$) and neither
232 “temperature” factor (PERMDISP: $F_{1,28} = 0.9624$; $p = 0,3942$). However, it is significant when
233 both factors are combined (PERMDISP: $F_{5,24} = 9.3558$; $p = 0.0002$), owing to the replicates at
234 S3 (Table 1). Specifically, the dispersion sequence —displayed by a multivariate dispersion
235 analysis (MVDISP)— was 0.85, 0.898 and 1.252 for S2, S1 and S3, respectively, and 0.895
236 and 1.105 for 20°C and 25°C, respectively. Regrettably, this analysis does not allow working
237 with two-way designs and, consequently, it is not possible to compare dispersion of cross-
238 factors.

239 Zooplankton assemblages were affected by salinity (PERMANOVA: $F_{2,24} = 8.6886$; $p =$
240 0.0001) and temperature ($F_{1,24} = 6.6257$; $p = 0.0001$). The interaction was also significant ($F_{2,24}$
241 $= 2.0248$; $p = 0.0372$). PERMANOVA pair-wise tests agree with the nMDS ordination:
242 communities differ between temperatures at S1 ($p = 0.0078$) and S2 ($p = 0.0073$). In contrast,
243 at S3 no differences between temperatures were detected ($p = 0.2849$). For a given temperature,
244 either 20 or 25°C, communities differ between salinities ($p < 0.013$).

245 An analysis of similarity percentages (SIMPER) shows both the *typical* taxa for each treatment
246 (Table 2) as the *discriminant* taxa among groups (Table 3). SIMPER shows the overall average
247 similarity for each treatment and defines the contribution that each species makes to the
248 similarity within the group. For example, the average Bray-Curtis similarity between all pairs
249 of replicates in treatment at S1-20°C is 68.29, made up mainly of contributions from just two
250 taxa: Ostracoda (36.93, i.e., 54.09% of total) and *Pleuroxus letourneuxi* (22.07, i.e., 32.32%),
251 with a cumulative contribution of 86.41% of the total within- group similarity.

252 Average similarities agree with the nMDS plot and PERMDISP analysis: the groups with the
253 highest similarity are S1-20°C (i.e., 68.29) and S2-20°C (i.e., 67.27), whereas the groups with
254 the lowest ones are S3-20°C (i.e., 45.64) and S3-25°C (i.e., 27.03). Ostracoda is the main taxon
255 in all treatments except at S3, where rotifers and *A. salinus* have the highest contribution (Table
256 2). *P. letourneuxi* is a characteristic species of S1, especially at 20°C, while *A. salinus* is typical
257 of S2 and S3.

258 Furthermore, SIMPER analysis allows defining the discriminatory species for each pair of
259 groups, that is, which species contribute to the differences between zooplankton assemblages
260 (Table 3). For a better understanding of the results, the test is performed for the main factors
261 rather than for each pair of treatments. That is, we look for discriminatory taxa among salinities
262 and between temperatures instead of among treatments. In this case, dissimilarity values are

263 displayed instead of similarities. For a better interpretation of the Diss/SD ratio (column 6),
264 abundances averages (fourth-square transformed) of the compared pair are also provided
265 (columns 3 and 4). When the aim is to identify species that contribute the most to the
266 differentiation between groups, the focus should be in the Av. Diss. column; they will tend also
267 to be the species with the larger abundances. But if we are looking for the best indicator of the
268 differences between those groups the Diss/SD ratio should be also considered, since it can
269 some-times pick out species which are completely absent in one group and with very consistent
270 presence in the other, but with low abundance (Clarke & Gorley, 2015). This is the case of *P.*
271 *letourneuxi*, only present in S1 and in just one replicate of S2 (Fig. 2), which become in the
272 most discriminant species between S1 and S2 and the second one most discriminant between
273 S1 and S3 (Table 3). Ostracoda is also a discriminant taxon since its abundances decrease when
274 salinity increase (Table 3, Fig. 2 and 4). Regarding to temperature, most of the rotifers are
275 discriminant species since they are more abundant at 25°C than at 20°C (Table 3, Fig. 2 and 4).

276 Ostracods abundance decrease with salinity and increase with temperature (Fig. 2 and Table
277 4.). Neither salinity nor temperature significantly affected the abundance of *A. salinus*, but it
278 was higher at S3 than at S1 in the treatments at 20°C (Tukey's pot-hoc test: $p = 0.044$; Fig.4 and
279 Table 4). Abundance of rotifers increases with temperature but it is not affected by salinity (Fig.
280 2 and Table 4). *P. letourneuxi* abundance increases with temperature and, in general, it is only
281 present at the lowest salinity (Fig. 2, Fig. 4 and Table 4).

282 ***Effect of salinity and temperature on diversity***

283 Table 5 and Fig. 5 show the results of several two-way ANOVAs testing the effect of salinity
284 and temperature on richness and Shannon-Wiener's diversity index. Richness was significantly
285 affected by those variables, but in a non-linear way. Indeed, interaction was statistically
286 significant: (i) richness reduced gradually at 25°C when salinity increased, whereas at 20°C

287 salinity did not affect richness, (ii) richness was higher at 25°C than at 20°C, except at S3, in
288 which not significant differences between temperatures were found. Consequently, temperature
289 and salinity had a combined effect on taxonomic richness. In contrast, these variables had no
290 observable effect on diversity. Nevertheless, even though there were not statistically significant
291 differences among treatments, diversity displayed a similar trend to richness.

292

293 **DISCUSSION**

294 Mediterranean wetlands are a highly fluctuating environment both seasonally and year-on-year.
295 Biota living in these water bodies have developed strategies to survive and develop in such
296 variable and unpredictable conditions. In this context, we studied which zooplankton
297 assemblages emerge from egg bank under different salinity and temperature scenarios. We
298 analyzed the cumulative abundances and taxa composition after 60 days of incubation in the
299 laboratory. The same sediment was incubated which allows us to focus on the effect of
300 temperature, salinity and its interaction, reducing the potential effects of other possible
301 confusion factors, such as ionic composition, hydrological patterns, geographical position, etc.

302 ***Role of temperature and salinity on zooplankton assemblage***

303 Temperature and salinity determined the species composition and abundances in a non-linear
304 way. The composition of the community was strongly determined by salinity at both
305 experimental temperatures. In contrast, the magnitude of the temperature effect depended on
306 salinity; the communities at 20 and 25°C differed between them at the two lowest salinities,
307 whereas no clear effect of temperature was detected at the highest salinity. In general, salinity
308 decreased total abundance but this decrease was especially marked at 25°C.

309 The results obtained are schematized in Figure 6. Overall, Ostracoda and *P. letourneuxi* would
310 dominate the community at the lowest salinity. At the opposite end *A. salinus* and rotifers would
311 become more important. At an intermediate salinity, Ostracoda and *A. salinus* dominate as
312 transition taxa. If we focus on temperature, then the results suggest that the species most tolerant
313 to salinity at high temperatures are the copepod *A. salinus* and the rotifers *H. fennica* and
314 *Brachionus* sp.

315 Consequently, the cues triggering the end of the dormancy state may be crucial for determining
316 the zooplankton assemblages in aquatic ecosystems. Once the community has emerged from
317 the egg bank buried in the sediment, the succession will be determined not only by the
318 physicochemical variables but also by biological factors, that is, who and how many are at a
319 given time can determine those ecological succession. In this sense, Castro (2004) found that
320 in a very extreme dry hydrological cycle, with salinity values higher than 200 g/L and
321 temperatures even upper 30°C, the plankton community structure in Laguna Honda was
322 physical-controlled, whereas in a wet period, with lower salinity ranges, the community
323 structure was controlled by biological factors (i.e. dominance of grazing, competition, etc.).

324 The interaction observed between temperature and salinity on community composition and
325 taxonomic richness might be an emergent property from the physiology at species-level since
326 temperature is known to have a species-specific interactive effect on salinity tolerance through
327 changes in their metabolic rate (Lee & Bell, 1999) and osmoregulatory ability (Aladin & Potts,
328 1995).

329 Salinity may reduce the rate of population growth of the keystone species *Daphnia pulex*
330 (Bezirci et al., 2012). In this respect, in previous research, a shift was seen from the dominance
331 of large cladoceran species at low salinity, with a broad-sized feeding spectrum, to the
332 dominance of smaller and less efficient grazer species at higher salinities, that is, copepods

333 (mainly calanoids), small cladoceran and rotifers (Heerkloss et al., 1991; Jeppesen et al., 1994,
334 2007). According to the findings in these studies, the calanoid *A. salinus* and the small
335 branchiopod *P. letourneuxi* were, along with the Ostracoda and rotifers, the most abundant
336 organisms to emerge from the sediment of this saline pond; whereas the presence of larger
337 cladocerans (*D. magna* and *D. mediterranea*) is anecdotal. This result is corroborated by the
338 data obtained by Castro (2004) in the same ecosystem; in which daphnids species appeared in
339 Laguna Honda at low density with low salinity levels. A shift to the extensive dominance of
340 rotifers when salinity increased was also observed in other enclosure experiments (Jeppesen et
341 al., 2007).

342 Some authors suggest that climate change could modify the size structure of zooplankton to
343 favor small-sized species (Molinero et al., 2006). In this sense, we have observed that rotifers
344 are favored at 25°C, although their abundance is drastically reduced to S3. Once again, the
345 results agree with the observations of Castro (2004), who found a high abundance of rotifers in
346 Laguna Honda in the summer season.

347

348 ***Role of temperature and salinity on diversity***

349 As happened to species composition and abundances, salinity and temperature determined
350 richness of zooplankton in a non-linear way. Richness increased with temperature, except at the
351 highest salinity where similar richness was detected at both temperatures. Similar results were
352 reported by Kaya and co-workers who in a field study found that temperature positively affected
353 the richness of rotifers (Kaya et al., 2010); although this effect was clear in freshwater habitats,
354 it was not observed at higher salinities. In the same way, Conde-Porcuna and colleagues (2018)
355 found also that the effect of salinity on hatching success of resting eggs of rotifers depended on
356 the temperature. At 15°C the hatching success of most rotifers species decreased with salinity

357 whereas at 25°C the relationship was quadratic with a maximum in the middle salinity (Conde-
358 Porcuna et al., 2018). This last finding agrees with the rotifers abundances we have observed at
359 the same temperature, 25°C. Under controlled laboratory conditions, Bailey and colleagues
360 (2006) studied the effect temperature and salinity had on cumulative abundance and the species
361 richness that emerged from zooplankton resting eggs from different sediments in ship ballast.
362 In a similar way to our results, they found that the salinity effect was temperature dependent,
363 although the direction of the effect was case-specific; interaction between these variables was
364 only significant for half of the different type of sediments, and even in two trials the
365 combination of high salinity and high temperatures led to more eggs hatching than at the other
366 exposures (Bailey et al., 2006). In contrast, recent findings by Mabidi and colleagues (2018),
367 from a lab incubation sediment experiment, are overwhelming and conclusive: a rise in salinity
368 drastically reduced both the abundance and taxa richness of crustaceans emerging from egg
369 banks in the wetlands of a semi-arid region in South Africa (Mabidi et al., 2018).

370 The richness of branchiopods in our experiments was very low and in concordance with field
371 studies in similar endorheic areas, as explained below. Boronat and colleagues (2001) studied
372 cladoceran assemblages from 44 endorheic bodies of water in Central Spain which displayed a
373 wide salinity gradient. At the boundary between the mesosaline and hypersaline status, the
374 cladoceran assemblage they found consisted of exactly the same species that hatched from our
375 sediment, that is, *D. magna*, *D. mediterranea* and *P. letourneuxi*. As these authors indicated, *D.*
376 *mediterranea* and *P. letourneuxi* are typical in Spanish endorheic lakes and are of biogeographic
377 interest due to their restricted Circum-Mediterranean distribution. These are usually
378 accompanied by other more widespread species, mainly the eurioic *D. magna* (Boronat et al.,
379 2001).

380 While in several field studies, the specific richness of zooplankton has been observed to decline
381 as a result of salinity (Boronat et al., 2001; Schallenberg et al., 2003; Brucet et al., 2009; Alcorlo

382 et al., 2014; Lin et al., 2017), the same could not be said for temperature, influence of which
383 was not so clear. Some authors did not find any significant relationship between this variable
384 and zooplankton richness (Lin et al., 2017) or on the hatching of resting-eggs (Burian et al.,
385 2016). In other studies, an inverse relationship has even been observed between zooplankton
386 richness and temperature (Pomati et al., 2012). Consequently, the response of zooplankton
387 resting eggs to temperature is not clear since different research show different trends.

388 It should be noted that although we found temperature and salinity have a significant effect on
389 species richness, the same was not observed for diversity. This observation was in keeping with
390 the findings of Paturej and Gutkowska (2015) who saw salinity had a significant negative effect
391 on the richness and abundance of zooplankton, but they did not observe any relationship
392 between salinity and diversity (measured with Shannon's index) (Paturej & Gutkowska, 2015).

393

394 **Conclusions**

395 Our findings confirm the hypothesis that the coexistence of different species living together in
396 a fluctuating saline pond was strongly determined by temperature and salinity, which have a
397 combined effect. Salinity was more determining on community structure than temperature, such
398 as López-González et al (1998) observed in column water from the same ecosystem. Although
399 the community was always dominated by smaller and less efficient grazer species, the
400 zooplankton assemblage changes with salinity and temperature. Thus, Ostracoda and *P.*
401 *letourneuxi* would dominate the community at the lowest salinity. At the opposite of the
402 gradient *A. salinus* and rotifers would become more important. At an intermediate salinity,
403 Ostracoda and *A. salinus* dominate as transition taxa. At high temperatures, the species most
404 tolerant to salinity was the copepod *A. salinus* and the rotifers *H. fennica* and *Brachionus* sp.
405 According to our field observations, *A. salinus* is a highly eurythermal and euryhaline species,
406 allowing it to dominate the community during all seasons (Jiménez-Melero, 2007). Regarding

407 richness, it was generally affected by salinity (decreasing) and temperature (increasing). In
408 contrast, diversity was not affected.

409 The enormous heterogeneity we have observed at S3, for both within and inter-treatments,
410 suggests that at a high salinity the structure of the emergent community is highly unpredictable.
411 In this respect, Winder and Schindler (2004) warned that climate change affects biological
412 processes in different ways, and it is therefore difficult to forecast how ecosystems will respond
413 to this phenomenon (Winder & Schindler, 2004). The indirect effects of global warming, such
414 as changes in salinity, will have a larger influence on brackish lagoon ecosystems than the
415 increase in temperature per se (Brucet et al., 2009; Akbulut & Tavşanoğlu, 2018). In terms of
416 population level, the phenotypic plasticity or individual variability of some life traits increases
417 under conditions of stress (Carlotti & Nival, 1991; Jiménez-Melero et al., 2005, 2007, 2012).
418 This phenomenon might be translated as an emergent property at community level, which gives
419 rise to different taxonomic compositions under identical environmental conditions, as suggested
420 by the high variability between replicates at the S3-25°C incubations. Our results suggest that,
421 under the current global warming scenario, increased temperature and salinity might lead to
422 unpredictable changes in species composition and to a decrease in species richness of saline
423 endorheic wetlands.

424

425 **STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS**

426 **Authors contribution**

427 All authors contributed to the study conception and design. R.J. and F.G. sought financial
428 support. R.J., J.M.R. and F.G. designed the study. R.J. and J.D.G. did fieldwork. R.J., D.J.,
429 J.D.G. and J.M.R. performed lab work. R.J. and D.J. did the statistical analyses. R.J. and J.M.R.
430 prepared the figures. J.D.G. and D.J. realized the taxonomical identification of the organisms.

431 R.J., D.J. and F.G. wrote the initial draft of the manuscript. All other authors critically reviewed
432 the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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437 **Conflict of interest**

438 The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

439 **Data availability statement**

440 Data are available from the lead author upon reasonable request: rmelero@ujaen.es

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601 **TABLE 1.** Pairwise comparisons from a test of homogeneity of dispersions (PERMDISP). p-
602 values are shown on left-bottom of the table, t-student on right-top of the table. Significant
603 values are indicated in bold.

<i>p-value</i> \t	<i>S1-20°C</i>	<i>S2-20°C</i>	<i>S3-20°C</i>	<i>S1-25°C</i>	<i>S2-25°C</i>	<i>S3-25°C</i>
<i>S1-20°C</i>		0.058826	6.5715	1.8959	1.4594	4.9219
<i>S2-20°C</i>	0.9272		4.9374	1.6653	1.2872	4.5917
<i>S3-20°C</i>	0.0082	0.0086		1.9678	2.1954	2.2273
<i>S1-25°C</i>	0.1507	0.3286	0.0786		0.2729	3.0582
<i>S2-25°C</i>	0.2631	0.3584	0.0407	0.8048		3.2054
<i>S3-25°C</i>	0.0086	0.0091	0.0155	0.04	0.0079	

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606 **TABLE 2.** Results of the SIMPER analysis showing the overall average similarity for each
607 treatment and the contribution of each species to the similarity within group. Av. Sim means
608 average similarity provided by each species. Sim/SD is the ratio of the average contribution
609 (column 3) divided by the Standard Deviation of those contributions across the within-group
610 similarities. Cum. contrib. (%) is the cumulative contribution truncated at 80%.

Treatment and group average similarity	Taxa	Av. Sim	Sim/SD	Contrib. (%)	Cum. contrib. (%)
S1-20°C: 68.29	Ostracoda	36.93	9.58	54.09	54.09
	<i>Pleuroxus letourneuxi</i>	22.07	3.56	32.32	86.41
S2-20°C: 67.27	Ostracoda	49.56	5.99	73.67	73.67
	<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i>	17.71	1.15	26.33	100
S3-20°C: 45.64	<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i>	32.46	1.96	71.12	71.12
	Rotifera	6.11	0.62	13.38	84.5
S1-25°C: 55.50	Ostracoda	17.46	10.82	31.47	31.47
	<i>Gnesiotrocha</i>	8.44	3.75	15.21	46.68
	Rotifera	5.96	1.09	10.74	57.42
	<i>Pleuroxus letourneuxi</i>	5.53	1.00	9.96	67.38
	<i>Lecane luna</i>	4.07	0.59	7.34	74.72
	<i>Brachionus sp.</i>	3.88	1.15	6.99	81.71
S2-25°C: 58.62	Ostracoda	18.47	3.37	31.51	31.51
	<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i>	12.09	3.02	20.62	52.12
	<i>Hexarthra fennica</i>	12.03	0.94	20.53	72.65
	Rotifera	8.63	1.09	14.72	87.37
S3-25°C: 27.03	<i>Hexarthra fennica</i>	12.22	0.58	45.22	45.22
	<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i>	9.78	0.62	36.19	81.41

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612

613 **TABLE 3.** Results of SIMPER analysis showing the discriminant species between treatments
614 grouped by main factors (i.e., temperature and salinity). Meaning of every column is indicated
615 in the main text.

Pair of groups and average dissimilarity	Taxa	Av. Abund first group	Av. Abund second group	Av. Diss	Diss/ SD	Contr. (%)	Cum. contr. (%)
S1 vs. S2: 53.76	<i>Pleuroxus letourneuxi</i>	1.91	0.1	12.77	1.69	23.75	23.75
	Ostracoda	2.91	1.85	7.15	1.74	13.3	37.05
	Rotifera	1.21	0.94	6.47	1.02	12.03	49.08
	<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i>	0.63	1.00	4.67	0.95	8.68	57.76
	<i>Hexarthra fennica</i>	0.61	1.42	4.31	0.71	8.02	65.78
	<i>Lecane luna</i>	0.8	0.1	4.31	0.76	8.02	73.8
	<i>Brachionus sp.</i>	0.68	0.2	3.64	0.83	6.77	80.57
S1 vs. S3: 79.14	Ostracoda	2.91	0.3	18.78	2.74	23.73	23.73
	<i>Pleuroxus letourneuxi</i>	1.91	0.00	13.55	1.78	17.12	40.85
	Rotifera	1.21	0.42	8.31	1.43	10.51	51.36
	<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i>	0.63	1.08	7.18	1.13	9.08	60.43
	<i>Hexarthra fennica</i>	0.61	0.78	6.38	0.86	8.07	68.5
	<i>Brachionus sp.</i>	0.68	0.68	6.14	1.04	7.75	76.25
	<i>Lecane luna</i>	0.8	0.00	4.43	0.62	5.6	81.85
S2 vs. S3: 66.43	Ostracoda	1.85	0.30	18.01	1.81	27.12	27.12
	<i>Hexarthra fennica</i>	1.42	0.78	13.69	1.13	20.6	47.72
	Rotifera	0.94	0.42	11.26	1.46	16.95	64.67
	<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i>	1.00	1.08	7.84	0.90	11.81	76.48
	<i>Brachionus sp.</i>	0.2	0.68	7.19	0.78	10.83	87.31
20°C vs. 25°C: 59.38	<i>Hexarthra fennica</i>	0.24	1.63	13.14	1.04	22.13	22.13
	Rotifera	0.63	1.09	8.87	1.25	14.94	37.07
	<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i>	0.88	0.93	7.11	0.61	11.98	49.05
	<i>Brachionus sp.</i>	0.43	0.62	6.89	0.74	11.6	60.65
	<i>Gnesiotrocha</i>	0.00	1.05	6.25	1.21	10.52	71.17
	Ostracoda	1.51	1.87	5.03	0.84	8.47	79.64
	<i>Lecane luna</i>	0.07	0.53	3.02	0.56	5.09	84.74

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620 **TABLE 4.** ANOVAs showing the effects salinity and temperature have on cumulative
 621 abundance. When necessary, data were transformed to normalize them. For *P. letourneuxi* a
 622 Generalized Linear Model was performed, with Poisson distribution and log-link function.
 623 Bold indicates a 95% significance level. *df*: degrees of freedom.

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<i>Source</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Ostracoda (square root transformation)			
<i>Salinity</i>	2	28.689	< 0.001
<i>Temperature</i>	1	6.217	0.020
<i>Salinity x Temperature</i>	2	3.005	0.068
<i>A. salinus</i>			
<i>Salinity</i>	2	2.171	0.136
<i>Temperature</i>	1	0.324	0.574
<i>Salinity x Temperature</i>	2	3.757	0.038
<i>Rotifera</i> (sixth root transformation)			
<i>Salinity</i>	2	1.259	0.302
<i>Temperature</i>	1	18.136	< 0.001
<i>Salinity x Temperature</i>	2	3.627	0.042
<i>P. letourneuxi</i> (GLM)			
	<i>df</i>	<i>Wald X²</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Salinity</i>	2	47.971	< 0.001
<i>Temperature</i>	1	405.265	< 0.001

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643 **TABLE 5.** Two-way ANOVAs showing the effect temperature and salinity have on richness
 644 and Shannon-Wiener's diversity. Bold indicates a 95% significance level. *df*: degrees of
 645 freedom.

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<i>Source</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Richness			
<i>Salinity</i>	2	16.098	< 0.0001
<i>Temperature</i>	1	10.670	0.0033
<i>Salinity x Temperature</i>	2	8.725	0.0014
<i>Error</i>	24		
Shannon-Wiener's diversity			
<i>Salinity</i>	2	2.239	0.1283
<i>Temperature</i>	1	1.431	0.2433
<i>Salinity x Temperature</i>	2	1.630	0.2169
<i>Error</i>	24		

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648 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

649 **Figure 1.** Location of the five sampling stations. a) Orthophotograph of Laguna Honda in a
650 wet year (2013) and b) the most current orthophotograph available (2019) (Sistema
651 Cartográfico Nacional de España, 2013, 2019). c) Bathymetric map; the interval between
652 isolines is 0.5 m (modified from Castro et al., 2003).

653 **Figure 2.** Shade plot of taxa abundances in the 5 replicates of the 6 treatments. Data are
654 fourth-root transformed. Abundances are represented by a grey shading from white (the taxon
655 is absent) to black (the maximum data value in the matrix).

656 **Figure 3.** Non-metric MDS ordinations (with 2 and 3 dimensions) of zooplankton
657 assemblages in each replicate within each treatment. Data transform: fourth square.
658 Resemblance: Bray Curtis similarity

659 **Figure 4.** Abundance of ostracods, the copepod *A. salinus*, rotifers (both unidentified as
660 identified) and the branchiopod *P. letourneuxi*, accumulated after 60 days of incubation under
661 different treatments. S1: 14.40 mS/cm; S2: 24.78 mS/cm and S3: 34.61 mS/cm.

662 **Figure 5.** Interaction graphs comparing richness and diversity between treatments. Means
663 predicted by two-way ANOVAs (Table 5). Asterisks in black indicate significant differences
664 between main factors (salinity and temperature). Asterisks in gray indicate statistical
665 significance between levels of a given factor (Bonferroni test). * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$. Bars
666 show the standard error. Note that for a greater clarity the richness data shown in the figure
667 are un-transformed, although in the statistical analysis they were previously transformed.

668 **Figure 6.** Outline that summarizes the results, where the salinity gradient is shown from left
669 (S1) to right (S3) and the temperature gradient from bottom (20°C) to top (25°C).

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673 wet year (2013) and b) the most current orthophotograph available (2019) (Sistema
674 Cartográfico Nacional de España, 2013, 2019). c) Bathymetric map; the interval between
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697 assemblages in each replicate within each treatment. Data transform: fourth square.
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708 **Figure 5.** Interaction graphs comparing richness and diversity between treatments. Means
709 predicted by two-way ANOVAs (Table 5). Asterisks in black indicate significant differences
710 between factors. Asterisks in grey indicate statistical significance between levels of a given
711 factor (Bonferroni test). * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$. Bars show the standard error. Note that for a
712 greater clarity the richness data shown in the figure are un-transformed, although in the
713 statistical analysis they were previously transformed.

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720 (S1) to right (S3) and the temperature gradient from bottom (20°C) to top (25°C).

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Figure 3

